

SECTION A: Introduction

Briefly introduce yourself.

Purpose of the focus group: to hear about students' experiences of the lessons – students' own thoughts and opinions.

No right or wrong answers. We are evaluating the lessons, not the students. We are interested in hearing both things that they liked and things that they did not like about the lessons.

They may not agree with each other about somethings. That's not a problem. But sometimes we may ask them if they agree with something that someone said, just to get a sense of whether everyone had the same experience.

Tell students how long the session will last (at least an hour).

Tell students that:

- *We want to record the session so we can be sure of what you said.*
- *We will not attach names to the notes or recording.*

Ask if students have any questions.

Start recording if given consent.

SECTION B: Intended effects, unintended effect, and transfer

1. First impressions of the lessons (for opening up)

Think back to when you started these lessons, what were your first impressions?

Notes

2. Intended and unintended effect

2.1 What are the most important things you have learnt from the “Be smart about your health” lessons?

Narrative summary, with quotes

2.2 Please tell us about **any disadvantages of the lessons**, in your experience.

Probe only if none has mentioned any of these:

- Misunderstanding
- Conflict (students and teachers, parents, or other authorities)
- Distraction
- Stress, or other uncomfortable thoughts or feeling
- Wasted time or resources

Narrative summary, with quotes

3. Transfer of learning

3.1 Have you used anything you learned in the lessons in your home / when you are with your friends / when you are with your family? **If so, please tell us about it.**

Prompt: Have you **taken something learned** in the lessons **and used it in a different subject or field?**

4. Barriers and facilitators for learning the resources

Question(s)	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>4.1. Which kinds of students benefitted most from the “Be smart about your health”</p> <p>Prompt: high, average, and low performers?</p>		<p>STUDENTS</p> <p>Differentiated instruction</p>
<p>4.2. How were you/your fellows student motivated to learn the lessons?</p> <p>To the extent motivated: What seemed to motivate you?</p> <p>To the extent unmotivated: Why do you think made you unmotivated?</p>		<p>STUDENTS</p> <p>Motivation to learn new materials</p>
<p>4.3. Do you think you and your fellow students were able to read and understand the “Be smart about your health” resources</p> <p>Probe: What was hard for you e.g lesson # or words What was easy for you e.g lesson # or words</p>		<p>Students’ ability to read and understand the material.</p>
<p>4.4. Could you describe how you attended “Be smart about your health” lessons</p> <p>Probe: - Reasons for attending less frequent/more frequent - Attendance of “Be smart about your health” lessons compared to other lessons at school</p>		<p>Students’ attendance or reasons for poor attendance (eg, long distance to school or inability to pay school fees).</p>

<p>4.5. Could you describe your attitudes when learning the resources?</p> <p>- Attitudes towards learning, towards authorities, towards science, towards critical thinking</p>		<p>Students' attitudes towards learning, towards authorities, towards science, towards critical thinking</p>
<p>4.6. Do you believe the content of the "Be smart about your health" lessons?</p> <p>If so, why? If not, why not?</p>		<p>Students' beliefs about the content</p>
<p>4.7. In your opinion, how did home environment affect you regarding learning the "Be smart about your health"</p>		<p>The extent to which the students' home environment encourages or discourages learning from the lessons.</p>
<p>4.8. How did other students (your peers) affect the learning "Be smart about your health" lessons?</p>		<p>Positive or negative attitudes of other Students towards the material.</p>

5. Wrap-up

Is there anything else you would like to discuss about these lessons?

Narrative summary, with quotes

Stop recording and thank them.